

stirring was continued for an additional 30 min. The reaction mixture was washed successively with ice-cold HCl (10%), saturated NaHCO_3 and brine solution. The organic layer was dried over calcium chloride. Evaporation of the solution gave the product (IV, 22 g), which was used as such without any further purification.

Ethyl 2-carbethoxy-8-(tetrahydro-2'-pyranyloxy)-octanoate (V): A solution of the mesylate (IV) was added to a sodium malonate, prepared from 2.53 g of sodium and 16 g diethyl malonate, in benzene (250 ml), and was heated on water bath for 10 hr. The contents were decomposed with cold water and extracted with benzene. The extracts were washed with water and dried. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure to produce diester (V), 18 g in 53% yield b. p. $183-85^\circ/7$ mm, ν_{max} 1725 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl). (Found: C, 62.28; H, 9.56. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 62.75; H, 9.36 %).

Ethyl 8-(tetrahydro-2'-pyranyloxy)-octanoate (VI): A mixture of the diester (V), 17.5 g and NaCl (4.5 g) in DMSO (100 ml) containing a few drops of water, was heated on oil bath at 160° for 4 hr. The contents were cooled and then added to cold water and extracted with pet ether. The extracts were washed with water and dried. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was vacuum distilled to produce the monoester (VI), 9g in 66% yield, b. p. $150^\circ-55^\circ/7$ mm. (Found C, 66.5; H, 10.20. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 66.14; H, 10.36%).

8-(Tetrahydro-2'-pyranyloxy) octanol (VII): A solution of the ester (VI, 22g) in dry ether (50 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred suspension of LAH (3.5 g) in dry ether (400 ml), during one hour. After the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was stirred for 4 hr at 50° . Thereafter, the contents were poured into an ice cold solution of sodium potassium tartrate and worked up in the usual manner. After the removal of the solvent, the residue upon distillation under vacuum gave the carbinol (VII, 14 g) in 83% yield, b. p. $145-50^\circ/7$ mm. ν_{max} $3380, 1040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-OH). (Found C, 68.20; H, 11.50. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.78; H, 11.38%).

8-(Tetrahydro-2'-pyranyloxy) octanol (VIII): Chromium trioxide (20 g) was added to a stirred solution of pyridine (51.6 ml) in dry methylene chloride (100 ml). The yellow coloured complex thus formed was stirred for 13 min at room temp. Then added alcohol (VII), 7.7 g) in dry methylene chloride (10 ml). A tarry black deposit separated immediately. After stirring for 20 min it was poured into ice cold water and extracted with methylene chloride and dried (CaCl_2). The solvent was distilled off and the residue chromatographed over alumina using pet ether as eluent. The product so obtained was distilled under

reduced pressure to obtain the aldehyde (VIII, 4.5 g) in 60% yield, b. p. $130-35^\circ/5-7$ mm, ν_{max} 17.25 cm^{-1} (-CHO). (Found: C, 68.10; H, 10.75. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 68.38; H, 10.59%).

Ethyl 10-(tetrahydro-2'-pyranyloxy)-trans-2-decenoate (IX): Sodium hydride (864 mg) was placed in diglyme (30 ml). Ethyl α -diethylphosphonoacetate (4.05 g) was added below 20° with stirring and the solution was stirred until gas evolution had ceased. To the resultant yellow solution was then added aldehyde (VIII, 3.5 g) slowly below 10° . After the addition, the solution was further stirred for 1 hr and then heated at 60° on a water-bath for half an hour. The product was extracted with ether after decomposing with excess of ice cold water. After removal of the solvent, the residue on distillation under reduced pressure gave (IX, 2.93) in 66% yield, b. p. $160^\circ-65^\circ/8$ mm. IR showed peak at 975 cm^{-1} (trans double bond). (Found: C, 68.75; H, 10.43. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 68.42; H, 10.13%).

Ethyl 10-hydroxy-trans-2-decenoate (X): A mixture of pyranyl ether (IX), 2.8 g, PTS (2g) and methanol (50 ml) was heated for 2 hr and the contents were cooled. After removing the alcohol, the aqueous phase was extracted with ether and washed with NaHCO_3 solution. The solvent was then evaporated and residue on distillation gave the alcohol (X, 2 g) in 93% yield, b. p. $155^\circ-60^\circ/7$ mm; ν_{max} $3400, 1040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-OH). (Found: C, 67.70; H, 10.15. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.25; H, 10.35%).

Trans-10-hydroxy-2-decenoic acid (I): The unsaturated ester (X, 2g), NaOH (0.6g) in water (1 ml) and methanol (5 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 hr on a water-bath. Methanol was removed under diminished pressure and the product was diluted with water. The unreacted material was removed by extracting with ether and the aqueous phase was neutralised with hydrochloric acid and extracted several times with ether. The extract was dried over sodium sulphate and solvent expelled to give the crude acid (I, 1.5 g) in 85% yield. The acid was recrystallised from pet ether, m. p. $64.5^\circ-65.5^\circ$. Lit(5) records m. p. $64^\circ-65^\circ$. The purity of the compound (I) was checked through tlc (single spot). ν_{max} $3460, 2950, 1710, 1660, 1440, 1375, 1280, 1215, 1180, 1095, 1050, 990$ and 893 cm^{-1} (Found: C, 64.15; H, 9.45. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 64.49; H, 9.74%).

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